

EMPLOYEES STRESS MANAGEMENT IN JM FRICTECH INDIA PVT LTD, CHENNAI, TAMILNADU: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Stress is a frustrating condition where it contains an excess of work and an overload which reduces the concentration, mentality and the normal working condition of any students. This study examines the impact of stress on students’ and stress management among students. The main objectives were to ascertain or identify the extent to which stress affects students’ academic success, health and general lifestyle, as well as to inquire about the effects of existing stress in students. A quantitative method was used in gathering and analyzing the data. For this purpose, questionnaires were distributed to students, who consisted of Post Graduate qualification. In addition it investigated in most satisfying event of an employee in the job, why employees stay and leave the organization. Data were collected through a field survey using a questionnaire from the employee groups, namely Professionals, Managers and Non-managers from organizations covering JM Frictech India Pvt ltd.

About Us JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd:

JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd (JMI), Established in 2008 as a joint Venture between M/s Jimmying Frictech Co Ltd - Korea and NTC Engineering Services Pvt Ltd - India. Design, Develop, Test and Manufacture of Wet Brake & Wet Clutch System with its actuation parts (both Mechanical & Hydraulic Brake Parts). JMI is the most preferred supplier to all Tractor OEM’s in India and we also supply to Construction & Material handling equipment’s segments. JMI exportsto various OEM’s in SouthAmerica, China and other parts of the world.

Manufacturing Facility:

JMI believes in self-contained facilities with High Precision CNC Controlled Machines and SPM’s to ensure the products as per specification.

- Capabilities of Design, Develop, Test & Manufacture the Wet Brake & Clutch System from “One Roof”.
- Friction Material (paper, carbon, Kevlar etc.) chosen from its widest range suitable to the application.
- Products are manufactured with “on line” Checking / testing features keeping the criticality of the final product.
- Brake and Clutch are critical for functioning of the end product/ equipment, JMI ensures defect free part with inbuilt “Poke Yoke “System in assembly. Integrated global experience in these part.
- Accredited with ISO 9001:2008 / ISO, 14001:2004 / BS-OHSAS, 18001:2007 Certified Organization.
- Quality is the way of life at JMI and we benchmark with global quality & standard.

Review of Literature:

Mathew (2017) Stress has a variety of meaning to people in the workplace. To the production manager in a industry, it may be the tension of missing the shipping date of a large order for a major customer. To the business executive, it may be frustration associated with the inability to acquire sufficient short-term loans from banks to cover the operating needs, and so on.

D’Souza (2017) Today’s leaders not only live and work at a faster pace but also must also deal with uncertainty and change. They need effective methods for coping with the kind of stress that affects anyone in leadership positions. People popularly identify managing directors or chief executive officers as those most susceptible to stress and disease. However, people at all levels of management find themselves exposed to comparable pressures.

Jha (2017) in his study on jobs stress and employee strain in India executives explains the pattern of stress and strain in three work groups, namely production, personnel and data processing divisions in an organisation. Results indicated that job future ambiguity had negative effect on job satisfaction in all the three groups. The patter of stress in the three groups was different among different levels of management. Among different levels of managers, the diddle level managers had more role ambiguity than others did.

Reddy and Ramamurthi (2018) in their study on the relation between stress experience on the job-age, personality and general ability analysed the influence of age, personality and general ability of the individual in the perception of stress. It was found that only age influenced the perception of stress. There was only very limited contribution of personality and general ability of the individual to the intensity of stress experience of the individual.

Berhem et al (2019) in their study on A New Model for Work Stress Patterns, describe that the role of ambiguity is the main source of work stress and self-knowledge as the main coping strategy to overcome work stress. Work stress is believed to be one of the most important factors affecting productivity.

Kang (2019) in his study on Stressors among Medical Representatives: An Empirical investigations, tries to investigate the various stressors related with the job of a industry employees. The results showed interference of job in personal life, unsupportive colleagues, work load and continuous pressure for improved performance have been found to be causing stress among the medical representatives.

Statement of the Problem:

Stress is one of the most important things that play a major role in human life. Since all the companies depend upon man power, it is one of the important issues to be taken care of and also it has become a major concern of the modern times. Stress can cause harm to employee's health and performance. Work related stress may lead to sickness, high turnover and high absenteeism. Job stress is a condition arising from the interaction of people that force deviate from their timing. So, it becomes necessary for every organization to know about the level of stress among the employees and its consequences so that the company can overcome it.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objectives:

- A Study on stress management towards JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd with reference to Chennai

Secondary Objectives:

- To know the level of stress existing among employees.
- To identify the factors causing stress among employees.
- To understand the consequences of stress on job performance.
- To understand the impact of stress on physiological and psychological aspects of employees.
- To give suitable suggestions to overcome stress.

Hypothesis of the Study:

The hypothesis set for the study is

- H0 - Employees are Satisfied
- H1 - Employees are not satisfied

Research Design:

“A Research Design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with the economy in procedure”. The research design adopted for the studies is descriptive design. The researcher has to describe the present situation in order to know the behavior of the consumers. Hence descriptive research study is used. Descriptive research can only report what has happened and what is happening.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology is a systematic way to solve a research problem; it includes various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying the problem along with the logic behind them. The present study was conducted at JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd at Chennai.

Method of Data Collection:

Data in the study are of two types:

- Primary data
- Secondary data

Sampling Population:

The aggregate elementary units in the survey are referred to as the population. Here it covers the entire customers of JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd.

Sample Size:

The study based only on the opinion and expectation of employees. Total number of sample taken for the study is 109 respondents. The study is done based on the opinions of the sample taken at random, the size of which is 109.

Statistical Tools Used:

- Percentage analysis
- Chi Square.
- Correlation

Limitations of the Study:

- This study was conducted 109 employees of the industry.

- Few employees and executives were not responded very much because of their busy of work schedule.
- Rating behavior on an appraisal of employee is quite difficult
- The research study is limited to day shift employees only

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Their Work Stress Leads to Illness

Work Stress Leads to Illness	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Stronglyagree	35	35
Agree	25	25
Neutral	15	15
Disagree	19	14
StronglyDisagree	15	11
Total	109	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above data indicates that 35% of respondents Work stress leads to illness were strongly agree and 25% were Agree and 15% were Neutral and 14% were Disagree and 11% were Strongly Disagree.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Their Mental Stress

Mental Stress	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Stronglyagree	15	14
Agree	25	23
Neutral	34	31
Disagree	20	18
StronglyDisagree	15	14
Total	109	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above data indicates that respondents work load leads to mental stress 14%wereStrongly agree and 23% were Agree and 31% were Neutral and 18% were Disagree and14%wereStronglyDisagree.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents for Over Come of Stress

Overcome Stress	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Meditation	20	18
Training	30	28
Refreshment	40	37
Other	19	17
Total	109	100

Source Data: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above data indicates that respondents for overcome stress 18% were meditation and 28% were training and 37% were refreshment and 17% were other.

Conclusion:

The present study was conducted at JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd. The aim was to find the stress levels, personality type of the employees. This was done using a detailed questionnaire. The study revealed that fall under low stress category only a small percentage is highly stressed & needed prevailing in the organization to some extent. At the end of the study, we can conclude that through there are signs of stress among the employees & such stress is affecting their behaviors, it can be controlled & reduced effectively. This can be done by giving counseling & incorporating the suggestions given here in at individual & organization level.

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